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Summary Report: Canadian Research Data Repositories and the Re3data Repository Registry

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Canadian Data Repositories Landscape Working Group

Digital Research
Alliance of Canada

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Project Summary

The goal of this project was to review and update existing Canadian repository entries in the re3data repository registry, as well as to identify new repository candidates and coordinate their submission to the registry. 153 potential repositories were identified and submitted for review to the re3data editorial team based on group-specified criteria. Additionally, the project aimed to highlight the value of the re3data repository registry for different stakeholders within the Canadian research data community. A list of recommendations has been developed for researchers and data service providers on how to improve the discoverability and accuracy of their data repositories via re3data.

Project Objectives

- ▶ Provide a baseline for Canadian research data repository inventory efforts.
- ▶ Support the coordination of existing Canadian research data repository inventory efforts.
- ▶ Support the discoverability and promotion of Canadian research data repositories through indexation in established repository registries.

Project Overview

As researchers intensify their efforts to share their data in order to support open science and comply with data availability requirements, more Canadian research data repositories are coming online and producing new challenges for those looking to reliably discover Canadian research data outputs. Research data repository inventories provide an important balancing force in this ecosystem, as they help describe the range of Canadian data repositories available to different users and facilitate the integration of repositories into broader discovery systems for digital research outputs at both national and international levels [1]. In April 2021, a short-term Canadian Data Repositories Landscape Working Group was formed within the Digital Research Alliance of Canada's Network of RDM Experts to survey Canadian data repository inventory efforts, investigate sustainable methods for tracking Canadian data repositories, and promote Canadian data repositories through established registries such as re3data and FAIRsharing.

Over 2021-2022, the group conducted a landscape analysis of current Canadian repository inventories, evaluated the varied selection criteria used to construct these inventories, and proposed a way forward to construct a combined inventory of Canadian research data repositories. During this period, the group identified its own inclusion criteria [2] for their combined inventory and employed a repository tracking methodology that recognized the quality of existing repository inventories, the unique disciplinary expertise of its members, and the importance of improving the representation of Canadian research data repositories in leading supranational repository registries. While this inventory project was never intended to comprehensively describe the Canadian research data repository landscape, it was hoped that

a concerted effort to improve the level and accuracy of descriptive information on Canadian research data repositories in leading registries could encourage spillover benefits for Canadian repository owners, researchers, and librarians across the country. In order to encourage productive outcomes for these stakeholders, the working group opted to prioritize the use of the re3data registry as a preferred source for Canadian data repository information. In large part, this decision was made to more formally recognize re3data's strong editorial practices, its considerable coverage of the Canadian repository space, its ongoing collaborations with varied members of the Canadian research data community, and its integration into internationally recognized digital research infrastructure projects such as OpenAIRE [3]. As such, the efforts of the group took into account the necessity of working in parallel with re3data's [registration requirements](#) and [metadata schema](#) when tracking new and existing repositories.

To undertake the project, group members reviewed existing Canadian repository entries in re3data as well as current inventories of Canadian repositories (such as the Canadian Association of Research Libraries Inventory of Canadian Repository Platforms, the Portage Access-Limited Data Discovery Working Group Repository Inventory, and the FRDR Discovery Service Inventory) against its inclusion/exclusion criteria for the inventory project. In addition, new repository candidates were identified and documented in tracking sheets by members of the group through structured web searches, research data indexes (DCI, Google DataSet Search), and the querying of generalist repositories (Dryad, Zenodo, Figshare, etc.).

Once recommended changes to existing re3data records and new potential repository candidates had been documented and finalized, these recommendations were submitted to the re3data editorial team (see submitted lists under relevant documentation section).

Recommendations

Repository Owners

- Canadian repository owners not already indexed in re3data should consider submitting a registration request (<https://www.re3data.org/suggest>) to the registry in order to help researchers discover and use the unique research data sets they disseminate.
- Canadian repository owners should notify re3data of any major changes to access policies for research data offered through their platforms via the "Submit a Change Request" included in individual registry entries.

The Alliance/Network of Experts

- Every three years, consider running an environmental scan on the repository landscape by reviewing existing Canadian data repository inventories and producing new lists by province or territory with the help of data stewards and data librarians from across the country.
- On a yearly basis, consider issuing reminders to the Canadian data community around the added value offered by the re3data registry to repository owners seeking additional visibility and discoverability.

Relevant Documentation

[Re3data Submission - Canadian Research Data Repositories Existing Inventories](#)

[Re3data Submission - Canadian Research Data Repositories New candidates](#)

References

[1] P. Webster, “Canadian Data Repository Inventory: White Paper for Canada’s New Digital Research Infrastructure Organization”. *Digital Research Alliance of Canada*, Dec. 14 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://alliancecan.ca/sites/default/files/2022-03/peter-webster-canadian-data-repository-inventory-white-paper-for-ndrio.pdf>

[2] Canadian Data Repositories Landscape Working Group, “Canadian Data Repository Landscape Working Group Inventory Project Criteria”. [Online] Available: <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1A98OzYrHU36l1ypFsD8S-pfIMtoUFR6ixL8sE363wUA/edit?usp=sharing>

[3] N. Rettberg, “re3data.org and OpenAIRE sign Memorandum of Understanding”. *OpenAIRE*, Aug. 8 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://www.openaire.eu/re3data-and-openaire-sign-memorandum-of-understanding>